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Research Article

**CHANCES OF ADVERSE EFFECTS AND CAUSES OF FALLS
IN THE POSTMENOPAUSAL FEMALES IN LAHORE,
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Background: The purpose of this investigation is to analyze the adverse effects of falls in females after menopause. In this study 200 females having post menopause were added in the study.

Methodology:

The study was of cross sectional type. The ages of the women added in the study were about 50 years. All the women added in the study were the inhabitants of Lahore. Expedient sampling was the methodology used for the selection of women for the investigational study in Lahore. Females that have already undergone any type of therapy, surgery or hormonal substitution were not included in the study. Disable females were also excluded from the study.

Results:

The scale used for the measurement of chances of fall in females was Berg Balance scale. The adverse effects produced in females by fall are assessed by giving a question paper to every patient. Females filled the question paper regarding their situations and risk factors. All the information obtained after receiving the filled question papers was analyzed by SPSS. The version 20 of the SPSS was used for the assessment. Females with average ages between 58-62 were included in the experiment. Most of the women added in the study were house inhabitants while small numbers of females were engaged in any job. About 75% females were house holders and remaining was doing some work. The high chances of fall were due to one main reason that was the presence of diabetes in females. It has been investigated that in the females suffering from diabetes have more chances of fall as compare to normal females who does not have diabetes. 7% more risks of fall were seen in diabetic women.

Conclusion:

The second main reason of plunge in females was deafness and third was incontinence. The dread of diminishing was also seen a big cause of declining in postmenopausal females. Sudden variations in blood pressure and muscular issues also cause the medium drops in females. This study was aimed to find out the causes of falls in the post menopausal females. The main reason that causes the fall in females were as listed below: diabetes, deafness, inability to stop urination, horror of drop out etc. as more of these reasons were present in females causes more numbers of falls in females.

Keywords: Falls, Postmenopausal, Risk factor, Women**Corresponding author:****Wajiha Tayyab,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Drop outs in females' causes many problems in females and may prove dangerous for their health. When the females stop their menstrual cycle a turn down in muscular pressure was seen in women. [1] The deficiency in elasticity of muscles causes the high chances of falls. It has been stated by the prose that many older females are at high risk of uneasiness of drop outs and this trepidation is the main cause of drop outs. It has been noticed that this fear of falling is more frequent in females as compared to males. [2] So this may cause the falling in females.

In the recent year 25% falls was seen in the females. There are more chances of drop outs in females as compared to males. From the 4th century weakness of bone has been seen in the females. In females' weak bones, loss of elasticity in strength of muscles has been noticed at their young ages. These symptoms are more common in females as compare to males. Loss of muscular elasticity was observed after some time in males and it is less powerful in males as compared to females. The loss of muscular power is slow process in males and is long lasting as compare to females. [3] Additionally, falls due to horror of falling are more frequent in women as compare to men. The patients survived from falls shows some adverse effects in them these effects included: wounds in tissues, limited workout, weakness in bone and joints, horror of again falling, self inefficacy and limitations in physical and communal activities. These persons may show less self assurance. [4]

It has been observed by Tinetti and associated that there are higher chances of falls in females who have already passed through some persistent disorders. In aged females greater numbers of drop outs was seen because persistent diseases were more common in age's females as compared to younger females. Drop outs and bone weakness are connected with each other and causes the breakage of bones and joints. The age limit is not directly connected with the drop outs. [5] Falls are related with the variations occurring in the individuals with the presence of diseases and various changes. There are high chances of drop outs are present in females whose legs are this having less skin, balance problems and use of more than three drugs. Chances of bone damage because of drop outs are more common in females as compared to males. The process of dropping out in males and females are changed. To limit drop outs we

should utilize sedative medications. These medications also lessen the pressure, convulsions, vigilance and bewilderment etc. [6]

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The study was of cross sectional type. It was arranged in the region of Sheikh Zayed Hospital Lahore. The study was started in September 2017 and ended in January 2018. 200 females were included in the study. The average age of the females was between 58-62. Samples were gathered from different areas of Lahore. The excluded criteria included the females who does not undergo stoppage of menopause still, women less than 50 years of ages and the women that are not the inhabitants of Lahore etc. females that underwent any kind of therapy or hormonal imbalance and disabled or injured females were not added in the study.

All the data and knowledge about the investigation study was given to the participants and a written permission was taken from all the participants. A question paper was given to every participant and data about every patient was obtained in written form. Patients included in the study were based on their own will. No financial gain or any kind of profit was offered to the participants of the study. Information was individually gathered from every participant. The person who collected information about the drop outs from the participants are conscious about the study. Connection of corporeal mass and drop outs was calculated by using body mass index. All the information regarding the falls including the height of the patient, its mass, fractures, bone injuries, use of any drugs etc was gathered from each patient by the help of a question paper given to each participant. Information obtained was assessed by the use of SPSS. The version of SPSS 20 was utilized.

RESULTS:

In this study 200 females were added. The average ages of the females added in the study were 58-62 years. 75% females were living in houses all the time while left 25% females were doing some work outside. Chances of drop outs were connected with the ages of the women. Older females have more chances of drop outs as compare to younger females. It has been suggested that age and BMI have no relation with each other. This relation has been shown in the following table.

Table 1 Relationship between age, BMI and BBS

Variables	BBS
Age	-0.25
BMI	0.04

This value is important if the p is less than 0.01.

To assess the effects of chances of drop outs between greater drop outs groups and average drop outs groups a logical deterioration was carried out. It was stated by the experiment carried out that there is the variation of 32% and 38% between the chances of drop outs in the two groups. Hg chances of drop outs were seen in the patients having diabetes. So diabetes is considered the most common cause of fall in females. Females having diabetes are more vulnerable to drop outs as compared to non-diabetic females. The second most frequent contributor of drop outs in females was deafness. There are 5% more chances of falls in deaf females as compared to normal ones. The third risk of drop outs was inability to stop urination. There are 4.9% more risks of drop outs in females who cannot stop their urination. The

females who are doubtful about the drops out are more vulnerable to drop outs as compared to the females who don't have the fear of drop outs.

The cause of average falls is the disability of muscular contraction. So it has been concluded that females who have muscular issues, spasms or flaw of muscles have more chances of average drop outs. There are 3.12% more chances of average drop outs in females having muscular issues as compared to females who don't have any issues related to muscles. The other cause of average drop out was variations in blood pressure. The females having high or low blood pressure are 2.42% more facing the drop outs as compared t the females who have average blood pressure. This has been shown in table 2.

Table 2: Model of logic deterioration that forecasts the similarity of greater chances of drop outs and average drop outs in the women

Variable number	B	SE	Wald	Odd percentage	Inferior	Superior
Group having greater chances of drop outs						
Diabetes	2.14	0.55	14.41	8.44	2.82	25.33
Deafness	1.61	0.72	5.23	5.04	1.24	20.27
Inability to stop urination	1.62	0.75	4.65	5.01	1.14	21.68
Horror of drop outs	1.47	0.69	4.63	5.02	1.10	17.45
Group having average chances of drop outs						
Issues related to muscles	1.15	0.58	4.00	3.14	1.03	9.60
Blood pressure	0.89	0.39	5.25	2.42	1.14	5.13

The females who take special drugs have more chances of drop outs. Polypharmacy also enhances the chances of drop outs in women.

Table 3: Relationship between drugs and drop outs

Variables	BBS	Medications of cardiac disease	Use of sleeping tablets	Drugs of blood pressure	Polypharmacy
BBS	-----				
Medications of cardiac diseases	-0.22	-----			
Use of sleeping tablets	-0.15	0.14	-----		
Drugs of blood pressure	-0.18	0.13	0.19	-----	
Polypharmacy	-0.35	0.20	0.22	0.32	-----

DISCUSSION:

The falls in females after the stoppage of menopause may cause serious complexities like fractures, fractures of tissues, and injuries in the head area. This study was organized to analyze the adverse affects of drop outs in females after the stoppage of menstrual cycle. [7]

It has been stated by Deandrea and his associated that fall are related with the enhancement of ages in individuals. It means that the chances of drop outs are greater in older individuals especially in women. When the age of a female increase 5 years, the chances of falls increase to about 2.13%. [8]The chances of drop outs are greater in women as compared to men. When an individual fall for the first time he has more chances of falls as compared to the person who did not fall for the first time. This occurs because of horror of falls out which increases the chance of drop outs. A study was organized by Schwartz and associated. He stated that diabetes is the most common factor that causes the increased rate of drop outs in patients. [9] Diabetic females have more chances of falls as compared to females without diabetes. Another study carried out by Wallace and associated stated the same findings that diabetic patients have more chances of falls. Maurer and associated also stated that in diabetic patients the chances of fall are 78% while in the patients having no diabetes have 30% chances of fall. [10]

Viljanen and associated relates the risks of fall with deafness. Persons having less hearing capacity are more likely to fall as compared to the persons have no issues related to hearing. The study recently studied also founded that the second most frequent factor of falling in females is loss of hearing or deafness. [11] Recommend disability to stop urination is also related with the chances of falls. Females who can't stop frequent urination have 1.75% more chances of drop outs as compared to normal ones. In the recent research the 4th most frequent cause of falling is the falling for the first time. It has been found that if a person falls for the

first time he will fall again and again because of the horror of falling. Horror of drop outs increases the risk of falling up to about 4.45% as compared to the women who have not fear of falling. [12]

CONCLUSION:

Cross sectional study was carried out to find out the chances of falling in post menopause females. The most frequent cause of falls in women is diabetes, diabetic patients are found to face more falling rates as compared to non diabetic females. The other causes of falling are less rate of hearing, disability to stop urination and horror of falling again and again etc. when these risk factors are enhanced they causes more rates of falls in patients.

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